

A Qualitative Exploration of Patients' Satisfaction with Doctors in Sukkur City.

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Abstract: *This research paper seeks to explore the level of Patients' satisfaction with doctors within the Sukkur city of Sindh, Pakistan. Seven factors which are general satisfaction, technical quality, interpersonal manner, communication, financial aspects, accessibility and convenience, and time spent with doctor is taken into account for this purpose. The sample of the study is patients and or their attendants in the different hospitals and clinics of Sukkur city. As this is a qualitative research paper therefore 15 interviews and 20 surveys were conducted from the respondents. The results were analyzed through the qualitative software of Nvivo 10, where nodes were formed, coding was done and finally matrix coding query was run in order to interpret the results. It has been found in the results that patients' satisfaction level has significant relationship with the technical quality, accessibility and convenience, and financial aspects. Whereas other remaining factors such as general satisfaction, interpersonal manner, communication, and time spent with doctor does not have significant relationship with patients' satisfaction.*

1. Introduction

The importance to study patients' satisfaction can be seen from the literature review of Patient satisfaction by Aharony and Strasser, where they had observed that different researchers consider Patient satisfaction important because: Satisfied patients will keep on using health care services, Satisfied patients will retain their association with their particular doctors or hospitals, Satisfied patients fulfill their medical regimens (as well as medications), Satisfied patients contribute in their own treatment, and Satisfied patients do collaborate with their health care providers (Aharony L, 1993). By considering all these aspects by different researchers it has been important to study that what causes a patient to be satisfied or dissatisfied with their health care providers.

Satisfaction can be defined as a consumer's opinion about any product or service that how much pleasurable experience it provides to its consumption related fulfillment, simply it's an assessment of a product or service that leads to some affecting rejoinder. A conclusion is drawn on basis of how sound the service was offered, and the consequences of this conclusion is pleasure or displeasure if satisfaction or dissatisfactions occurs respectively (Schommer, MO: 2003;316-30).

According to (Hulka, Zyzanski, Cassel, & Thompson, 1970) patients' satisfaction is identified as "satisfaction" is the "attitude of patients to doctors and health care. Whereas broadly accepted definition of patient's satisfaction is a combined index of a person's evaluative opinions related to the quality of health care given from doctors and health care is imagined to symbolize the person's point of "satisfaction". Wolinsky 1976; Hines et al. 1977; Doyle and Ware 1977; Ware et al. 1918 (Locker & D. Hunt, 1978)

Thus this research paper seeks to explore the satisfaction level of patients within the Sukkur city of Pakistan. For this purpose different factors have been selected from the (Marshall, Hays, & Monica, 1994) in order to identify patients' satisfaction with doctors. Different hospitals and clinics were visited in order to collect data from the patients to meet the research objectives.

2. Literature Review

(Goel, Sharma, Bahuguna, Raj, & Singh, 2014) Have examined in their research the level of satisfaction among patients attending OPD (outpatient Department) in public health facilities in North India & they found well height of satisfaction at the OPD, thus the policy makers should spot now on correlates of satisfaction namely, accessibility to health facility, physician care, physical environment and management of health care facility.

(Alturki a & M. Khan, 2013) Research states that Patients satisfaction level with the Pharmacy is quite good in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, but their research has also concluded that Saudis are least happy through the services of pharmacy as compare to the Egyptians and other countries because some of the demographic issues are basis of increase or decrease in satisfaction level.

(Zamil, Areiqat, & Tailakh, 2012) The study in this paper measures the affect of the medical services Quality on satisfaction of patients in the Health care facilities of government and private zones in Jordan. Authors have used standard measure of SERVPERF that is planned particularly to evaluate service quality in diverse Service sectors. The study has found that health services quality has the impact on patients' satisfaction further they have found that:

- Private hospitals services are better than government hospital services.
- The awareness towards health services quality has lowest mean as compare to other services quality.

The results of their research are same as (Irfan & A., 2011) that Private hospitals services are better than government hospital services according to the patients 'perception in Pakistan.

(Grøndahl, 2012) Has mentioned in his paper that there are complexities in evaluating the perception of quality of concern and patients' satisfaction and the conditions associated with these concepts. However, in order to measure these variables the author has taken help of both qualitative and quantitative data. Questionnaire consisting of four variables Quality from Patients' Perspective (QPP); Sense of Coherence scale (SOC); Big Five personality traits – the Single-Item Measures of Personality (SIMP); and Emotional Stress Reaction Questionnaire (ESRQ) was used for quantitative data and interviews were taken for the purpose of qualitative data. The main findings of the study show that Individuals' opinion about medical care quality and their satisfaction are diverse topics therefore it was suggested that medical care staff need to get conscious about that while setting up and conducting nursing care.

(Naseer, Zahidie, & Shaikh, 2012) In Pakistan patients' experiences and expectations are important factors to determine patient satisfaction. Different demographic factors such as age, gender, and social class are considered as important factors in determining satisfaction levels of patients. Adding together lack of space, independence, participation in decision making, poor communication, and sanitation direct towards terrible patient experience by combining all these satisfaction of patients decreases. This analysis focuses on the difficult and interconnected determinants of patient satisfaction with hospitals and doctors in Pakistan.

(Omer, Cockcroft, & Andersson, 2011) In this review of paper authors have conducted two cross sectional studies in which government implemented Hospital improvement initiative (HII) which included the behavior changing training for employees, disposing of waste and procurement, and recommended arrangements and then two surveys in the years 2000 and 2003 were carried out for the purpose to assess the affect of HII on patients' experience and satisfaction in governmental hospitals. Also the outer groups monitored hygiene and confidentiality systems, and also went to some of the houses in society as a sample in order to know their

perceptions about the use of hospital services. The data was analyzed in the Multivariate analysis and hence they concluded that:

- HII has positive improvement on patient's experiences
- There is also less availability of medicines in public hospitals
- Monitoring patients' experiences and satisfaction is feasible and is quite useful for assessing interventions

(Ziaei, Katibeh, Eskandari, Mirzadeh, Rabbanikhah, & Javadi, 2011) A study was conducted at an ophthalmic hospital to examine patient satisfaction with hospital and staff services and to know the affect of diverse proportions on the whole satisfaction and thus they suggested if services providers want to develop quality of health services from patients' point of view they should focus upon improving technical quality and patients' accessibility.

(Marcinowicz, Chlabicz, & Grebowski, 2009)The review of the paper provides insights on the ways that verify a satisfaction or dissatisfaction of patients and then to combine the patients' answers supported by their assessment of medical care. For this purpose a qualitative study was conducted in which 36 in-depth interviews with families of patients and doctors were carried out. The study found that patients were more concerned with the issue of interpersonal relationships with family doctors, while 40% gave equally negative and positive comments regarding aspects of healthcare. Whereas second most frequent category which was discussed was contextual factor that includes conditions of medical services in which two-third of the evaluation with was negative and people were less concern about the doctors' skills and personal qualities.

(Sajid, Ali, Rashid, & Ali, 2001) the paper is consist of two phases the first phase is identifying the dissimilarities between Services quality or its impact on Satisfaction of patients, the other phase deals through the perceptive of factors which are irregular in hospitals, especially in terms of process performance. For all this purpose a strategy was formulated that that can decrease those inconsistencies which are prevailing in the health care facilities.

3. Research Model

3.1 Theoretical Framework

According to PSQ-18 (Marshall, Hays, & Monica, 1994) seven different factors are taken to measure the patients' satisfaction. The PSQ-18 starts with the general satisfaction which includes the patients general level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction, the second factor is technical quality which is designed to measure the doctors experience, ability and the instruments availability along with way of examining and treating. The third factor is interpersonal manner which attempts to measure the doctors' behavior with patients whereas communication includes financial aspects which measures the access to doctor financially. The sixth component is time spent with doctor measures the time given to the patient, while last factor accessibility and convenience of patients with respect to doctors and medical care facility.

4. Research Hypothesis

H1: There is significant relationship between general satisfaction and patients' satisfaction

H2: There is significant relationship between interpersonal manner and patients' satisfaction

H3: There is significant relationship between technical quality and patients' satisfaction

H4: There is significant relationship between communication and patients' satisfaction

H5: There is significant relationship between financial aspects and patients' satisfaction

H6: There is significant relationship between time spent with doctor and patients' satisfaction

H7: There is significant relationship between accessibility & convenience and patients' satisfaction

5. Research Objectives

1. To explore the satisfaction of patients with doctors.
2. To find out level of patients' satisfaction with doctors.

6. Research Questions

1. What causes a patient to be satisfied with the doctors?
2. What causes a patient to be dissatisfied with doctors?

7. Research Methodology

7.1 Sample

Sample of the study are mainly the patients of different hospitals and clinics of Sukkur city, or the attendants with patients.

7.2 Data Collection Method

Interview and survey methods are used to collect the data, 15 interviews were conducted from patients or their attendants and 20 surveys were filled by the patients/attendants. Instead of using untested questionnaires PSQ-18 (Marshall, Hays, & Monica, 1994) were used.

7.3 Data Analysis Technique

To analyze the results of the data matrix coding query of Nvivo 10, the results were interpreted on basis of two different factors the first one is respondents' qualification and the second one is respondents' income level.

8. Results & Discussion

The two different basis were used in order to find out the results the one is qualification of respondents and the other is Income level of respondents but there were no such big difference in both the findings, according to them technical quality is the most considerable issue for the patients which contributes 23.17%, it means doctors ability, experience, availability of instruments and way of examining and treating are the highly influencing aspects to determine a patients satisfaction. While the second most considerable issue for the patients are accessibility and convenience to the doctors which

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